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Review Article

Cannabidiol In Medicine: A Comprehensive Review of Its Pharmacology & Pharmacognocny

Himani Kamde, Manjusha Meshram, Rishabh Meshram*, Maadhuri Nandgave

Chhatrapati Shivaji Collage of Pharmacy deori , Gondia (441901).

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ABSTRACT

CBD, a popular phytocannabinol, has shown potential in treating drug-resistant epilepsies and anxiety, chronic pain, and inflammatory disorders. Despite being restricted due to its physicochemical properties, CBD has shown promise in treating gut and lung diseases in vitro. However, overcoming these challenges requires improved formulations and delivery methods using technologies like self-emulsifying emulsions and Nano and micro particles. This review aims to address research gaps and obstacles in developing CBD-based therapeutics. Cannabis species contain cannabinoids, which produce over 100 naturally occurring chemicals, including δ -9-tetrahydrocannabinol (THC), cannabidiol (CBD), terpenes, and flavonoids. THC and CBD bind with cannabinoid receptors in the brain and organs. Metabolism depends on consumption route. Inhaled THC enters the bloodstream quickly, reaching the brain and organs. It is highly lipid soluble and rapidly taken up by fat tissue. CBD, with high lipophilicity, is rapidly distributed in the brain and organs. It is hydroxylated in the liver and excreted mainly in feces. The Study examines the morphological characteristics of *Cannabis sativa* L. Cv. White Widow, focusing on leaf morphology, plant structure, flower development, and trichome features throughout its life cycle. It investigates developmental responses to photoperiodic variations from germination to mature plant senescence. The study reveals a progression of complexity in leaf morphology, with a peak at the 12th leaf. Mature flowers display abundant glandular trichomes, with a significant increase in trichome density. Hermaphroditism occurs well after harvest.

INTRODUCTION

Cannabis sativa, or Indian hemp western Asia. The plant is cultivated for (subfamily *Cannaboideae* of family *Moraceae*), its medicinal properties and as a natural textile fiber.² an annual herbaceous plant native to central and

*Corresponding Author: Rishabh Meshram

Address: Chhatrapati Shivaji Collage of Pharmacy deori , Gondia (441901).

Email ✉: mmeshram203@gmail.com

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Fig.1

Cannabis is a complex plant with over 400 chemical entities of which more than 60 of them are cannabinoid compounds approximately 80 are biologically active, some of them with opposing effects. Cannabis is also the most widely used illicit drug in the world and its use has been associated with various mental health problems, particularly in the young.¹

Parts of the cannabis plant

Fig.2

Flower

The flowers of the female marijuana plant can be identified by their small teardrop structures, which consist of pistils attached to bracts. Cannabis flowers are usually covered with a frosty-looking coating of trichomes, with a heavier density of trichomes making for a more desirable flower.

Cola

The main part of the flower, at the end of a female plant's stem is composed of many small floral clusters. In general, the bigger, heavier, and more

densely covered in trichomes a cola is, the better quality it will be, although some cultivars will naturally grow flowers that are more loosely structured and airy.

Bracts

The small leaves that surround the reproductive cells of a female weed plant. When a female plant is exposed to pollen from a male marijuana plant, the bracts surround and shield the seed pod.

Trichomes

Marijuana trichomes are hairlike appendages found on the surface of the cannabis plant. Trichomes protect the plant from external stressors and contain resinous glands that create flavonoids, cannabinoids and terpenes—the chemical compounds that

give the marijuana plant its unique features and effects. Trichomes give cannabis buds a crystal-like sheen and make them sticky feeling.

Node

The point at which the stem and leaf intersect. Nodes can hold one or more leaves or offshoots. As explained below, nodes are important to be familiar with, as they are where cannabis plants begin to grow either pollen sacs (male cannabis plants) or pistils (female cannabis plants). Understanding the sex of a marijuana plant is crucial to the final product, since only female plants produce flowers and since non-pollinated flowers are far superior than pollinated buds when it comes to consumption.

Fan leaves

Leaves are important components of a weed plant, and there are actually a couple types of marijuana leaves. The large, protruding leaves that appear along the length of the plant are called fan leaves. These leaves are essential to the living plant's photosynthesis, but are always removed from the finished, harvested product.

Stem

The main support structure of the marijuana plant, the stem transports fluids, nutrients, and

information from the roots to the rest of the weed plant. The stem provides a foundation to give fan leaves access to the light they need to facilitate growth and carries the weight of heavy colas. The most relevant cannabis compounds are cannabinoids, which are formed by a terpene

combined with resorcinol (or a benzopyranic ring system, according to a different nomenclature). There are about 60 cannabinoids. The most important psychoactive compound is tetrahydrocannabinol (THC), particularly the isomer delta (Δ^9 -THC).

Fig. 1 Chemical structure of main cannabinoids in *Cannabis sativa*.

Different parts of the cannabis plant have different concentrations of these phytochemicals. For example, leaves and glandular trichomes in the bark contain the most potent cannabinoid metabolites. Flower buds are primarily rich in THC, CBD, CBC, and CBG.³

While THC is psychotropic, CBD, another phytocannabinoid present in the *Cannabis sativa* plant, is non-psychotropic and has witnessed widespread acceptance for the symptomatic treatment of various medical conditions. CBD has antipsychotic, anxiolytic, anti-seizure, and anti-inflammatory properties and potentially mitigates

some of the adverse psychotropic effects of THC by acting as a negative allosteric modulator of CB1 receptor.⁴

Classification Of Cannabis

Classification Of Cannabinoid

MORPHOLOGY

1. LEAF MORPHOLOGY

This investigation into the morphological characteristics of cannabis leaves during their development from seed germination to maturity revealed a distinct and organized pattern of leaf morphogenesis. After the expansion of cotyledons, the first true leaves (L1) were each one single

serrated leaflet, which served as an initial stage of leaf development. Subsequently, the second true leaves (L2) emerged, featuring three serrated leaflets each, marking a notable increase in leaf complexity. Nodes 3 and 4 produced leaves with five serrated leaflets (L3 and L4), further highlighting the progressive trend in leaflet formation. At nodes 5 and 6, the number of serrated leaflets continued to increase, resulting in leaves with seven (L5) and nine (L6) serrated leaflets, respectively. This developmental sequence depicted in Fig.3 clearly demonstrates the stepwise progression of leaflet complexity during the early stages of cannabis growth.⁷

Fig.3. Leaf morphogenesis in cannabis from cotyledon (c) to 25th true leaf (L25) in the main stem.

From—clto—L12, the plants were maintained under a long-day photoperiod. Starting from L13 and continuing thereafter, the plants were subjected to short-day photoperiod conditions.

1. Plant Architecture

During the growth under the long-day photoperiod, nodes 2–4 exhibited the presence of axillary buds, accompanied by a pair of leaves at each node showing the plants were in the juvenile phaseAdditionally, two stipules were observed flanking the base of the leaf petiole in node 5 and node 6, demonstrating the transition of the plants from the juvenile phase into the mature phase⁷

Phase-transition-related morphological changes. (A) Cannabis plants with stipules and opposite phyllotaxy, showing the vegetative phase; (B) Cannabis plants with bracts and solitary flowers, signifying the transition of the plants into the reproductive phase; (C) Cannabis plants with alternate phyllotaxy (red arrows show the alternate arrangement of leaves).

1. Floral Morphology

Upon transition to the short-day photoperiod, compacted inflorescences emerged at the apical regions of the main stem (after 10 days) and secondary- and tertiary-order branches (after 15 days). Cannabis inflorescences presented as complexly branched compound racemes. This distinctive structure is emblematic of monopodial

growth, featuring an enduring apical meristem and indeterminate axillary inflorescences of higher orders. Flower development at the apical regions of the main stem is shown in **Fig.5**. During flower development, prior to stigma elongation, a

profusion of glandular trichomes emerged on the perigonal bract encasing the ovary. As the inflorescences a reddish-brown shade Fig.57

Fig .5. Flowering progress in cannabis. Main flower after (A) 3 days, (B) 1 week, (C) 2 weeks, (D) 4 weeks, (E) 6 weeks, and (F) 8 weeks.

Chemical constituents of *Cannabis sativa* L. 47,48 Marijuana is the crude drug derived from the plant *Cannabis sativa* L. a plant that is currently accepted as belonging to a family (Cannabaceae) that has only one genus (*Cannabis*) with only one species (*sativa*) that is highly variable.

Cannabis has had a long history of use (over 5000 years) starting in Central and Northeast Asia with current use spreading worldwide as a recreational drug or as a medicine albeit unauthorized. Several historic reviews have been written on *Cannabis* use as a

Cannabinoids: 70 known (4 new)

The typical C₂₁ group of compounds present in *C. sativa* L. is known as cannabinoids and includes their analogs and transformation products (Razdan, 1987). Five different numbering systems have been used for the cannabinoids (Fig. 1; Eddy, 1965). Compounds in this review will be numbered according to these systems, or if needed, by using the Chemical Abstract Index numbering. The 70 known cannabinoids can be classified as follows:

Other constituents: 419 known (2 new)

The following chemical classes (number known) has been identified in marijuana: nitrogenous compounds (27), amino acids (18), proteins (3), enzymes (6), glycoproteins (2), sugars and related compounds (34), hydrocarbons (50), simple alcohols (7), simple aldehydes (12), simple ketones

(13), simple acids (20), fatty acids (23), simple esters (12), lactones (1), steroids (11), terpenes (120), non-cannabinoid phenols (25), flavonoids [23, including 2 new flavonol glycosides, namely kaempferol 3-O

Mechanism of action
Until the mid-12th century, the existence of human cannabinoid pathways was not understood. The discovery of THC and CBD led to identification of the signaling pathways. Evidence that THC interacts with a particular mammalian target was uncovered in murine neuroblastoma cells, which expressed upregulated adenylate cyclase in response to exposure to the compound or its synthetic analogues. This finding paved the way for the isolation and cloning of a G protein–coupled receptor that subsequently was named cannabinoid receptor type 1 (CB1).⁸ Cannabinoid

receptor type 2 (CB2) was later isolated from human leukemia cells.⁹ CBD was shown to directly exert activity at the CB2 receptor. Identification of these receptors led to the hypothesis that an endogenous cannabinoid system in the mammalian body, known as endocannabinoids, might also exist. The first endogenous cannabinoid ligand was then isolated from pig brain and named N-arachidonylethanolamine (AEA) or anandamide¹⁰. The second endogenous ligand was also isolated from intestinal tissue and named 2-arachidonoylglycerol (2-AG).^{11,12} Both AEA and 2-AG are arachidonic acid derivatives produced from phospholipid precursors through activity-dependent activation of specific phospholipase enzymes.¹³ A number of other endogenous ligands have since been discovered, including N-arachidonoyl dopamine, N-arachidonoyl glycerol ether, and O-arachidonylethanolamine.¹⁴

2-AG is mainly synthesized through activation of phospholipase C and subsequent production of diacylglycerol, which is converted to 2-AG by diacylglycerol lipase. 2-AG is primarily metabolized by monoacylglycerol lipase, leading to the formation of arachidonic acid and glycerol.¹⁴ CB1 and CB2 receptors are certainly the most well-known targets for AEA and 2-AG, which activate them with different affinity.

AEA has the highest affinity in both cases.¹⁴ Physiological or pathological stimuli induce synthesis and release of endocannabinoids, which can subsequently activate cannabinoid receptors. Therefore, endocannabinoids are synthesized and released “on demand” through the cleavage of membrane phospholipid precursors.

THC and CBD of the phytocannabinoid system can also bind to G protein-coupled cannabinoid receptors CB1 and CB2. CB1 receptors are particularly abundant in the frontal cortex, hippocampus, basal ganglia, hypothalamus,

cerebellum, spinal cord.^{15,16} and peripheral nervous system.¹⁵ They are present in both inhibitory GABAergic neurons and excitatory glutamatergic neurons.¹⁵ CB2 is most abundantly found on cells of the immune system, hematopoietic cells,¹⁷ and glia cells.¹⁶ CB2 is mainly expressed in the periphery under normal healthy conditions; in conditions of disease or injury, this upregulation occurs within the brain and CB2 is therefore expressed in the brain in unhealthy states.¹¹ CB1 and CB2 are also widely distributed in the cardiovascular system.¹⁸ Synthetic cannabinoids are typically consumed through smoking or in a concentrated liquid form. The negative effects of synthetic cannabinoids include palpitations, paranoia, intense anxiety, nausea, vomiting, confusion, poor coordination, and seizures. Interestingly, some individuals reported strong compulsions with persistent cravings to reuse a week after cessation and some reported withdrawal symptoms such as headache, nausea, and vomiting.¹⁹

Uses of Cannabinoids⁴⁶

Pain

Helping to Decrease Opioid Use Anxiety

Epilepsy Glaucoma

HIV/AIDS Symptoms Inflammatory Bowel Disease Irritable Bowel Syndrome

Movement Disorders Due to Tourette Syndrome

Multiple Sclerosis

Nausea and Vomiting Related to Cancer Chemotherapy Posttraumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD)

Sleep problems

Pharmacology of cannabidiol

PHARMACOKINETICS

OF

CANNABINOIDS

The pharmacokinetics of cannabinoids are reviewed by Agurell et al⁴⁹. and Maykut and others. About 50% of the THC in a joint of herbal cannabis is inhaled in the

mainstream smoke; nearly all of this is absorbed through the lungs, rapidly enters the bloodstream and reaches the brain within minutes. Effects are perceptible within seconds and fully apparent in a few minutes. Bioavailability after oral ingestion is much less; blood concentrations reached are 25-30% of those obtained by smoking the same dose, partly because of first-pass metabolism in the liver. The onset of effect is delayed (0.5-2 hours) but the duration is prolonged because of continued slow absorption from the gut.

Once absorbed, THC and other cannabinoids are rapidly distributed to all other tissues at rates dependent on the blood flow (Fig.6). Because they

are extremely lipid soluble, cannabinoids accumulate in fatty tissues, reaching peak concentrations in 4-5 days.

They are then slowly released back into other body compartments, including the brain. Because of the sequestration in fat, the tissue elimination half-life of THC is about 7 days, and complete elimination of a single dose may take up to 30 days⁵⁰.

Clearly, with repeated dosage, high levels of cannabinoids can accumulate in the body and continue to reach the brain. Within the brain, THC and other cannabinoids are differentially distributed. High concentrations are reached in neocortical, limbic, sensory and motor areas

Fig.6 Distribution of THC in the body. The distribution of THC after a single administration in plasma and body tissues. Note the 'biphasic' disappearance in plasma. The rapid phase (in minutes) indicates a rapid uptake of the drug by fat-containing tissues. The slow phase (in days) shows the release of THC by these tissues THC, tetrahydrocannabinol.

Cannabinoids are metabolised in the liver. A major metabolite is 11-hydroxy-THC which is possibly more potent than THC itself and may be responsible for some of the effects of cannabis. More than 20 other metabolites are known, some of which are psychoactive and all of which have long half-lives of several days. The metabolites are partly excreted in the urine (25%) but mainly into the gut (65%) from which they are reabsorbed,

further prolonging their actions. Because of the pharmacokinetic characteristics of cannabinoids — both the sequestration in fat and the presence of active metabolites — there is a very poor relationship between plasma or urine concentrations and degree of cannabinoid-induced intoxication. The discovery of cannabinoid receptors naturally stimulated a search for an endogenous ligand with which the receptors naturally interact. Such a substance was isolated from the pig brain by Devane *et al.* It was found to be chemically different from plant cannabinoids: it is a derivative of the fatty acid arachidonic acid

(arachidonyl ethanolamide) related to the prostaglandins (Fig. 7). This endogenous substance was named anandamide after the Sanskrit word for bliss, *ananda*. It has a high affinity for CB₁ receptors and has most of the actions of THC. Thus, the story of opium, opioid receptors and endogenous opioids is now repeated with cannabis, cannabinoid receptors and anandamides.

➤ PHARMACODYNAMICS OF CANNABINOIDS

Cannabinoids exert their effect by interaction with specific endogenous cannabinoid receptors,

Fig.7 Chemical structure of anandamides.

Two similar endogenous fatty acids have since been isolated (Fig. 7) and it now appears that there may be a whole system of multiple cannabinoid receptors and anandamide-related substances. Their physiological function has yet to be⁵³. appears that both anandamides and their receptors reside within neuronal lipid membranes and act as neuromodulators through intracellular G-proteins controlling cyclic adenosine monophosphate formation and Ca²⁺ and K⁺ ion transport. In this role the system may have important interactions

discovered by Devane *et al*⁵¹. Neuronal cannabinoid receptors are termed CB₁ receptors and have been found in rat, guinea pig, dog, monkey, pig and human brains and peripheral nerves. A second cannabinoid receptor, the CB₂ receptor, was identified by Munro *et al.* in macrophages in the spleen and is also present in other immune cells. The distribution of CB₁ receptors is very similar to that of injected THC and includes cerebral cortex, limbic areas (including hippocampus and amygdala), basal ganglia, cerebellum, thalamus and brainstem⁵²

with other neurotransmitters, including γ-aminobutyric acid, opioid systems and monoamines. In particular, THC has been shown to increase the release of dopamine from the nucleus accumbens and prefrontal cortex⁵⁴. This effect, which is common to many drugs of misuse (including heroin, cocaine, amphetamine and nicotine), may be the basis of its reinforcing properties and its recreational use. It is reversed by naloxone, suggesting an opioid link

Overview of CBD pharmacological effects

Disease	Effects	References
Cancer	In a variety of cancer models, with anti-proliferation and ant	i[20],[21],[22],[23]
	invasion effects; inhibits angiogenesis; enhances immune kil	l[24],[25],[26]
	induces autophagy-mediated cancer cell death; alleviates ca	

	pain; protects the body's normal cells etc.	
Infection	Inhibits the activity of Porphyromonas gingivalis; inhibit the activity of methicillin-resistant Staphylococcus aureus (Gram-positive bacteria or optionally anaerobic bacteria have a certain inhibitory effect)	[27],[28]
Depression	Antidepressant effects in a genetic rodent model of depression.	[29],[30],[31]
Anxiety Disorder	Reduce patients' social anxiety, relaxes muscle tension, improve patients' sleep; reduces restlessness and inattention; regulates mu and delta opioid receptors in cerebral cortical membrane homogenate.	[32],[33],[34] [35],[36],[37]
Pain	Treatment of patients with refractory central or peripheral nerve pain; attenuation of behavioral and glial changes in animal models of schizophrenia; analgesia and improvement of sleep quality in cancer patients.	[38],[39],40]
Epilepsy	Reduce the frequency of seizures, anticonvulsant.	[41],[42]

CONCLUSION

Cannabinoids are effective therapeutics for several medical indications if their specific pharmacological properties are considered.

There are over 100 cannabinoids, each with potential benefits that remain to be discovered. Some other areas of interest regarding treatment with cannabinoids include epilepsy, psychotic disorders, anxiety, and sleep disorders. Data shows acute CBD administration decreases experimentally induced anxiety in healthy humans.

RESULT: CBD shows promise for various health benefits but consumer should be cautious and informed. It's important to consult healthcare professional and choose high-quality, reputable products to ensure safety and effectiveness.

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